

The Role of Marketing Mix Elements In Online Purchase Intention

Online Satın Alma Niyetinde Pazarlama Karması Unsurlarının Rolü

Dilaysu Çınar / Doç. Dr.

İstanbul Beykent Üniversitesi, Meslek Yüksekokulu,
dilaysucinar@hotmail.com.tr

Serkan Altunay

Cimri Bilgi Teknolojileri ve Sistemleri A.Ş.,
serkan.altunay@hotmail.com

Abstract

The main purpose of this study is to examine the effects of digital marketing mix elements on consumers' online purchasing intention. In addition, the study examined whether online purchasing intentions vary according to the demographic characteristics of the participants. This study was conducted in Istanbul, Türkiye, and the population of the research consists of consumers who are 18 years of age and older and who have done or are doing online shopping at least once in a certain period of their lives. The convenience sampling technique was used in the research. The data for the research was obtained through a survey administered to 404 participants. The data from the study were analyzed using SPSS 26.0 and AMOS 24 programs. As a result of the research, it was revealed that physical evidence, process, product, promotion and human mix elements positively affect online purchasing intention.

Keywords: Digital marketing mix, online purchase intention, online consumer behavior.

Jel Code: M30, M31

Özet

Bu çalışmanın temel amacı dijital pazarlama karması unsurlarının tüketicilerin online satın alma niyeti üzerine etkilerinin incelenmesidir. Çalışmada ek olarak, online satın alma niyetinin katılımcıların demografik özelliklerine göre değişkenlik gösterip göstermediği irdelenmiştir. Bu çalışma İstanbul, Türkiye'de yapılmış olup, araştırmanın ana kütlesini 18 yaş ve üzeri, hayatlarının belirli bir döneminde en az bir kez online alışveriş yapmış veya yapmakta olan tüketiciler oluşturmaktadır. Araştırmada kolayda örnekleme tekniği kullanılmıştır. Araştırmanın verileri 404 katılımcıya uygulanan bir anket ile elde edilmiştir. Araştırmanın verileri SPSS 26.0 ve AMOS 24 programları kullanılarak analiz edilmiştir. Araştırma sonucunda, fiziksel kanıt, süreç, ürün, tutundurma ve insan karması unsurlarının online satın alma niyetini olumlu yönde etkilediği ortaya çıkmıştır.

mış olup, araştırmanın ana kütlesini 18 yaş ve üzeri, hayatlarının belirli bir döneminde en az bir kez online alışveriş yapmış veya yapmakta olan tüketiciler oluşturmaktadır. Araştırmada kolayda örnekleme tekniği kullanılmıştır. Araştırmanın verileri 404 katılımcıya uygulanan bir anket ile elde edilmiştir. Araştırmanın verileri SPSS 26.0 ve AMOS 24 programları kullanılarak analiz edilmiştir. Araştırma sonucunda, fiziksel kanıt, süreç, ürün, tutundurma ve insan karması unsurlarının online satın alma niyetini olumlu yönde etkilediği ortaya çıkmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Dijital pazarlama karması, online satın alma niyeti, online tüketici davranışı.

Jel Kodu: M30, M31

1. Introduction

The internet, one of the greatest inventions of developing technology, has become indispensable in our lives day by day. Changing habits and easy access to the internet enable consumers to shop and pay simply and quickly via digital applications (Baltes, 2016:33). The time consumers spend on digital applications is increasing day by day, so it is considered very important for businesses to deliver their marketing efforts to consumers through digital applications.

Today, as a result of the increasing competition between companies and consumers who see the brand as an identity, companies aim to present successful brands to the market in order to stand out

from their competitors, gain customers and retain their existing customers (Zaki and Masri, 2020:313). With the help of developing technology, businesses benefit from a number of strategies in order to win over consumers who have become more conscious, know what they want and seek quality (Wakjira and Kant, 2022:119). One of the most important of these strategies is the digital marketing mix. Today, consumers want high quality products or services, establish mutual relationships with product/service providers and purchase more value at a lower price. For this reason, businesses need to try to create marketing mix elements (Çipli, 2008: 26).

Fully integrated and coherent marketing mix strategies constitute a large part of a successful marketing strategy (Akroush, 2011: 146). Once the market has been successfully segmented, target market segments have been selected, and positioning strategies have been created, the marketer must continue to develop the marketing mix (Goldsmith, 1999: 181). Once the target market is selected, marketing managers need to develop a systematic plan for selling to customers and building long-term relationships. The marketing plan consists of decisions about product, price, promotion and distribution. These are the primary decision areas in which marketing managers allocate scarce business resources to achieve sales and profit goals (Goldsmith, 1999: 178).

Nowadays, online shopping means not only convenience but also desire and satisfaction. Consumers form purchasing intentions before purchasing products and services online. This intention emerges with current desires, needs and information (Stephen, 2016:19). Cultural, social, political factors and climate changes direct consumers to different products and services in terms of factors such as interest and taste. Knowing this orientation is important for sellers in terms of developing a marketing mix strategy. Online purchasing intention refers to consumers' online evaluations and behaviors regarding the product or service. Online purchase intention is at the core of the concept of online purchasing (Durna and Demirci, 2023: 412).

The more current and effective the data on the online purchasing intentions of e-consumers, the more successful it will be in developing a marketing mix strategy. For this reason, online purchasing intention and marketing mix strategies to be developed in parallel are among the issues that need to be researched. The aim of this study is to determine which element of the digital marketing mix elements affect online purchasing intention. In addition, the study attempted to measure whether online purchasing intentions differ according to demographic variables. In this context, the study conducted a literature review on the digital marketing mix and online purchasing intention and then conducted research on the subject.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Digital Marketing Mix

Businesses prioritize market conditions in an intensely competitive environment. Prioritizing market conditions also reveals another important factor for businesses that have accepted and implemented marketing management. This factor is the marketing mix, which is one of the main subjects of marketing. The concept of "Marketing Mix", which is one of the basic concepts of marketing theory, was first used in a study by James Culliton. Later, Neil Borden grouped it under twelve headings, including data collection and analysis, and thus stated that marketing mix elements can be listed in different ways (Sümer and Eser, 2006: 167).

Intense competition in today's market conditions has made it necessary for businesses to add new elements to their marketing mix. In this case, marketing mix elements increase depending on the company's goals, market conditions, product mix, etc. With the concept of mega marketing, Kotler suggested that a marketing mix much larger than the marketing mix known as the 4Ps would be beneficial for the competitiveness of businesses and suggested that power and public relations be included in the scope of mega marketing (Kotler, 2000: 17). Thus, the 4P marketing mix elements increase to "7P" according to the need. These are; product, price, place, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence.

Product decisions are among the primary decisions businesses make when developing their marketing mix. A product can be a physical object, a service or an idea. The concept of product mostly includes concrete products. To define it more comprehensively, the product can be physical objects, services, people, organizations, ideas, or a combination of all of these. (Kotler and Armstrong, 2011: 218). Product, in other words, is the basic component of the finished product marketing mix. It is the basic concept that determines the characteristics of the business and its position in the target market. It forms the starting point of all marketing activities. It is impossible to decide on price, distribution, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence without deciding on the product to be produced (Hasanov,2004,36). In the online environment, products are considered from three perspectives. These are physical products, digital products and services (Jamaludin, 2018:20). The product sold online has some differences compared to the products sold in a traditional environment. First of all, the product is offered online and can be easily found through search engines. Online product creates a distinctive motivation on customers. The website where the product is presented is richer in terms of content and design than its presentation in the traditional environment (Vynogradova and Drokina,2020:122). The

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most important element of the product title in digital marketing is whether the product is suitable for sale in the digital environment. What is its value to consumers? Is the firm's brand different from other brands? Are the firm's products or services renewed, necessary repairs made and after-sales service provided? Are necessary studies being carried out for those who will consume a firm's product or service digitally? Answers to questions such as these need to be given (Kingsnorth, 2017:9). Consumers should be able to examine and experience products online and accept the product as a part of themselves, so personalization is provided (Stokes, 2013:24). With the advent of digital products, packaging for intangible products has been eliminated. Again, with the internet, the information on the label is also available online. In order for online consumers to have positive feelings towards brands, the brand must first have a strong image. On the other hand, the online consumer's loyalty level decreases for products with low brand awareness (Baltes,2016:34). Other factors that affect the consumer's product purchasing behavior in the online environment are the increase in symbolic consumption, effective brand management and strong customer relationship management (O'Cass and Heirati, 2015:62). In the online environment, the consumer does not have the opportunity to examine the product with his five senses. This is one of the most important disadvantages of presenting products online. To eliminate this situation, the photo resolution must be high, the product must be photographed from multiple angles, the product photograph must be zoomed in (Fachriyan et al. 2022:145), and augmented reality applications must be used.

Price is defined as the representation of the exchange or unit value of the product or service in money. The meaning of price in marketing, which businesses can use as an important weapon, is the money that buyers must pay in order to have a product or service (Sümer and Eser, 2006: 115). Pricing products and services is one of the biggest and most complex decisions businesses have to make. There are various reasons for this. One of the most important reasons is that the relationships between consumers, competitors and the distribution network are complex. When making pricing decisions, the interaction between these three groups should be taken into account. Another difficult aspect of pricing decisions is that they have to be made quickly, without testing, even though they have a direct impact on profits (Peter and Donnelly, 2012: 57). It is necessary to pay attention to three important factors when making pricing decisions in the online environment. These are accuracy, relevance and segmentation (Pogorelova et al., 2016:6748). Price policies in the digital environment are quite dynamic. Thanks to a number of applications, it has become easier for consumers to compare product prices. This diversity on the inter-

net has increased the competitive environment. Especially for small sellers, adopting a flexible pricing strategy is very important in order to increase sales rates and get a share of the market (Stokes, 2013:24). The main pricing strategy used by companies in the online environment is the competitive pricing method. The possibility of online consumers accessing a large number of similar products forces businesses to gain a competitive advantage in terms of price. This is one of the most important advantages of selling in the online environment (Baker et al., 2001:122). In addition, consumers can compare prices on a single page via the internet. This situation similarly forces businesses to adjust their prices according to their competitors' prices (Chaffey,2019:371). In addition to offering products at lower prices, online pricing offers other advantages to the business. These are providing price flexibility, being able to change prices more easily, the absence of most costs in the traditional environment, the abundance of purchasing agencies, and the applicability of the reverse auction method (Lasi, 2021:173).

Place covers all processes of the product and/or service until it reaches the customer. Decisions such as sending customers to sales points where they are likely to purchase the product, where the product will be placed on the shelf at that sales point, and so on are also made under the control of the distribution staff. The purpose of distribution is to provide convenience to the consumer. (Kaplan, 2011: 214). Brands are now able to sell their products online. Thus, easy access to the global market has been achieved (Kingsnorth, 2017:11). E-place includes not only the online sales point but also the online contact point. In the online environment, the distribution channel is generally carried out between the producer and the end consumer through two intermediaries: the e-commerce site and the courier. In this context, the online distribution channel is carried out with fewer intermediaries compared to the traditional distribution channel. This situation makes it easier to find the same product at a lower price than in the traditional environment (Baltes,2016:36). In order for consumer purchasing behavior to be positive in the online environment, the distribution strategy must include the originality of the product group, the convenience and usability of the website, and customizability (Pogorelova et al., 2016:6749).

Promotional efforts have a great place and importance in reaching consumers, presenting their products and continuing their activities. Conscious, planned activities carried out through different channels to ensure the formation of a positive image for the business/product, to maintain the ongoing positive image, and to change the negative image are within the scope of promotion (Kaşıkçı, 2001:50). Products can be promoted with the help of the Internet, and with this promotion, more people can be reached than the number of people reached by

promotions made in traditional marketing. With on-line promotional activities, consumers are included in the communication process. In the next stage, it directs the online consumer to the site for purposes such as registering, making recommendations, and commenting (Baker et al., 2001:123). The cost of promotional activities carried out through online communication channels is lower compared to traditional communication channels. Due to its higher accessibility, promotional activities can be announced to more people. Promotional strategies can be personalized. The effectiveness of promotional activities can be measured more easily than in the traditional environment. Promotional campaigns can be carried out through numerous channels such as websites, blog sites, social networks and forums (Chaffey, 2019:376). E-commerce sites can carry out their promotional activities through a number of on-line marketing methods. These are; search network advertising, display advertising, search engine optimization, product aggregators, remarketing, email marketing, social media marketing, affiliate marketing online public relations, online discounts, promotions and loyalty programs (Vynogradova and Drokina, 2020:123). Promotional activities carried out online not only promote the product but also establish an emotional bond by increasing interaction between the online consumer and the brand. This increases the online consumer's trust in the brand.

The physical evidence consists of the environment where the service is performed, where the business and customers interact, and all kinds of concrete components that facilitate the realization and communication of the service (Hudson, 2008: 150). E-physical evidence defines any tangible component through which the e-commerce site and the online customer interact in the digital environment and is required for this interaction to be more effective and efficient. In this context, e-physical evidence is the sum of functions for the more comfortable provision, presentation and consumption of the service offered to online customers (Pomeroy et al., 2011:955).

Processes are mechanisms that transform inputs into outputs. Processes are the arrangements of resources that produce mixes of goods and services (Slack et al., 2007: 12). The e-process describes the digital distribution of the service performed online and the operating systems created for the service (Wilson et al. 2020:117). The e-process element is very important for the service developed for online consumers to be more effective and efficient. The e-process directly affects the consumer's online purchasing behavior and attitude towards brand satisfaction (Buhalis, 2008:611). Some processes that affect consumer purchasing in the online environment can be summarized as the product selection process, order processing time, packaging time, distribution time and delivery of the order at the specified time and quality.

People constitute an important dimension in the management of services, both as customers and employees (Raju, 2009: 50). People are an essential input for the business to achieve a competitive advantage and continue its sustainability (Lovelock and Wirtz, 2021:47). Factors such as the employee's staff, the employee's education and skill level, and the employee's characteristic structure directly affect the consumer's perception of service quality (Mohammad, 2015:105). All employees who provide service to customers in the e-commerce environment constitute e-personnel. In this context, sales personnel and call center personnel who communicate with consumers in the online environment, online consumers who have a consultant role, VIP consumers and producers who will affect the quality of the product are elements included in the definition of e-people (Vynogradova and Drokina, 2020:123). The strategies implemented for e-personnel affect the perception level of both internal customers and external customers towards the brand. In this context, it is necessary to focus on the personnel element in order to positively affect the online customer's perception of service quality towards the brand (Matura, 2018:215). Speed of responding to customers, speed of resolving complaints, level of use of smart bots are other human elements that affect consumer purchasing behavior in the online environment (Pogorelova et al., 2016:6749).

When the research conducted in the field of marketing mix is examined, it is observed that it will be more effective (Rafiq and Ahmed, 1995), will affect consumer preference (Kamau et al., 2015; Lin, 2011), will increase consumer satisfaction (Sarker et al., 2012), competitive advantage (Al-Debi and Mustafa, 2014) and consumer satisfaction when the marketing mix is expanded. The difference between this study and other studies is that the marketing mix elements are examined by adapting them to the digital environment.

2.2. Online Purchase Intention

Purchasing intention is defined as the consumer's planning to purchase a certain amount of a certain product or brand at a certain time (Çetin and Kumkale, 2016: 92). Online purchasing intention is defined as the consumer's willingness and involvement during online transactions (Akel, 2015: 21).

The first factor that affects consumers' online shopping is perceived value. Perceived value varies depending on the consumer. In e-commerce shopping, low price and high quality are basically priorities for the customer. It is determined that other elements vary in parallel with the environment and conditions to which the consumer is exposed. A practical delivery process is important for consumers who urgently need the desired product or service. Offering simple gifts to the consumer who does not feel

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the need to buy and involving her in the purchasing process in this way will create returns that increase the customer's happiness and satisfaction with the opportunity she receives (Leu, 2009:80). The second factor that affects consumers' online shopping acceptance and use of technology. In this context, as consumers' use of technology increases and their level of acceptance of innovations increases, their tendency towards online shopping increases.

The third factor that affects consumers' online shopping is consumer satisfaction. There are many factors that affect customer satisfaction in e-commerce. Many factors such as trust in online shopping, company image, and rapid solutions to customer demands and requests affect customer satisfaction (Babacan and Şimşek, 2018:68). The fourth factor that affects consumers' online shopping is consumer trust. Online trust can be defined as the consumer's intention to enter into an online shopping relationship with a particular online seller, and as a result, trust can lead to actual purchasing behavior (Ou and Sia, 2010:915). The fifth factor that affects consumers' online shopping is consumer loyalty. The loyalty of online consumers is the intention of the e-consumer to purchase from the same site in the future (Liu, 2012:205). The sixth factor affecting consumers' online shopping is related to perceived service quality. E-service quality is a concept that covers the effective and efficient shopping, purchasing and distribution processes of customers interacting with websites (Parasuraman, et al., 2005: 215).

The seventh factor affecting consumers' online shopping is perceived ease of use. Perceived ease of use positively affects online purchasing intention. Therefore, fewer technological systems that will help the website provide ease of use will enable consumers to create more purchasing intentions (Akel, 2015: 22). The eighth factor that affects consumers' online shopping is price. Price has long been an influential factor in consumers' decision-making processes. Electronic media, on the other hand, enable individuals to easily find the best price by comparing prices between different sites. Consumers often do not remember the unit prices of products or services. They direct price perceptions by comparing prices between sellers during the purchasing decision process and coding prices as "higher" or "lower." This affects purchasing decisions (Kim et al., 2012:243). The ninth factor affecting consumers' online shopping is related to perceived risk. Perceived risk theory mentions many dimensions of risk. There are financial risks, temporal risks, performance risks, psychological, physical and social risks. Therefore, increased perceived risk affects consumers' reluctance to shop. Online companies should understand risk perception and develop appropriate strategies to reduce risk perception in online shopping (Kim et al., 2009: 204). The tenth factor affecting consumers' online shopping is saving time. Customers can

shop online at any time of day. This allows consumers to save time. Thanks to online shopping, consumers can shop without leaving home, whenever they want and without the effort of visiting a store (Forsythe, 2006:59). The eleventh factor that affects consumers' online shopping is related to finding the appropriate product. One of the most important and successful online strategies today is to deliver products to customers waiting in long lines to receive service and to meet the demand for products that cannot be reached in physical or traditional stores (Scott, 2009:72). The twelfth factor that affects consumers' online shopping is related to the design of the website. It has been revealed that whether the websites established for shopping are useful or not directly affects consumers' desire to use the site. In other words, whether the sites are useful or not has an indirect impact on consumers' online shopping intentions (İşler et al., 2014:81). The thirteenth factor that affects consumers' online shopping is related to user comments. According to research, negative comments about the product or service affect consumers more than positive comments (Akdeniz and Özbölük, 2019:3106). The most important determining factor in online purchasing intention is the actual purchase. The actual purchase occurs as a result of both the quality of the website and evaluations made by the consumer (Poddar et al. 2009:442).

In addition to the above explanations, when research on the subject is examined, it can be seen that online search intention (Kim et al., 2004), online store environment (Chang and Chen, 2008), enjoyment, usefulness and compatibility (Lu and Su, 2009), perceived value (Escobar-Rodríguez and Bonsón-Fernández, 2017), culture (Peña-García, 2020), brand value (Febrian and Vinahapsari, 2020), virtual brand experience (Gabisch and Gwebu, 2011), brand equity (Beneke et al., 2016), brand awareness (Chen et al., 2011:124), perceived trust and value (Shareef et al., 2018), and perceived information quality (Jeong and Lambert, 2001) have a positive relationship with online purchasing intention. In this study, unlike other studies, the effect of digital marketing mix elements on online purchasing intention was tried to be examined.

3. Research Methodology

It has been observed that more and more scientific research has been conducted on online shopping in recent years, which has become increasingly widespread, has a critical importance for national economies, and also closely affects individual lives. Studies have also been conducted trying to explain online consumer behavior (Chan et al., 2003; Cheung et al., 2005; Cummins et al., 2014; Jayanti, 2024; Nugraha, 2024; Joshi, 2024; Railean and Savciuc, 2024) However, it has been observed that studies examining the effects of product, price, place, pro-

motion, physical environment, process and human factors on e-commerce shopping are rarely conducted (Mahendratmo and Ariyanti, 2019; Sugiarto et al., 2022; Wahyuni et al., 2023). Additionally, no study has been found in Turkey examining the effect of the digital marketing mix on online shopping intention. It is thought that the findings of this research will make a significant contribution to filling the gap in this field. By determining the factors affecting online purchasing intention, it will be possible to develop applications that will increase customer satisfaction and also enable the development of e-commerce. In this direction, this research aims to examine the effects of digital marketing mix elements on online purchasing intention. The study also examined whether online purchasing intentions differed according to the demographic characteristics of the participants.

This study was conducted with the participation of adults over the age of 18 who live in Türkiye and have done or are doing e-commerce shopping at least once in a certain period of their lives. Individuals who have not shopped on e-commerce sites and individuals under the age of 18 were not included in this study. The online shopping behavior of the individuals included in the research was examined in terms of product, price, place, promotion, physical evidence, process and people factors, which are defined as digital marketing mix elements. This research is limited to Türkiye. This research is limited also individuals who over the age of 18 and have shopped on e-commerce sites at least once in their lives. The subject of this research is limited to digital marketing mix elements and the intention to shop on e-commerce sites. This research is limited to the opinions of participants who volunteered to participate in this research during the time period when the research was conducted. Finally, this research is limited to the responses given to the scales in the survey form developed as a data collection tool.

In accordance with the purpose of the research, a quantitative research design was used and the relational survey design was used in the research. The population of the research consists of adults over the age of 18 who have online shopping experience in Türkiye. It has been stated that if the size of the universe is 100 thousand or more, the number of samples will be 400 (Israel, 1992:3). For this reason, in this research, it was aimed to reach a sample number of 400 by using convenience sampling technique and a sample number of 404 was reached. Importance was given to including participants of different genders, ages and education levels in the sample.

The data for the research was collected by the survey method. The survey form developed to measure the variables in the research model consists of three parts. In the first part, questions were asked targeting the participants' demographic information. The second section includes scales that aim to measure

seven digital marketing mix elements. The third section includes the scale that aims to measure consumers' intention to shop online.

The literature was scanned in detail and carefully to create scales that aim to measure the digital marketing mix element. In the foreign source review, it was seen that the scales used in the studies of Sudheer, Sudhir and Sudheshna (2017:39-45), Charastarakool (2020:1-44) and Mahendratmo and Ariyanti (2019:72-82) were compatible with the purpose of this research. A validity analysis of the scale was conducted and it was found that the scale loaded on seven factors with a KMO value of 0.53 and a high factor loading of 0.61. These scales were rearranged in accordance with the purpose of this research. The scales were translated into Turkish by an expert and reviewed for scientific suitability by another expert. This scale consists of 40 items prepared to measure seven digital marketing mix elements. The scale is a 5-point Likert type and the statements are answered as "strongly disagree", "disagree", "undecided", "agree" or "completely agree". In scoring, the answers given to the statements are coded as 1–2–3–4–5, from "I completely disagree" to "I completely agree". There are no questions directed in the opposite direction.

Kurt's study (2021:43-44) was used to create the online shopping intention scale. The scale developed by Kim and Lennon (2013:33-56) and also by Chang and Chen (2008:818-841) was adapted to Turkish by Kurt (2021:43-44). The scale, which was revised in accordance with the purpose of the research, was used for this research by obtaining expert opinion. The scale prepared to measure the intention to shop on e-commerce sites consists of two items. The internal consistency coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) of the scale was calculated as 0.67. The scale is a 5-point Likert type and the statements are answered as "strongly disagree", "disagree", "undecided", "agree" or "completely agree" according to the degree of agreement. In scoring, the answers given to the statements are coded as 1–2–3–4–5, from "I completely disagree" to "I completely agree". There are no questions directed in the opposite direction.

The data for the research was collected in January 2023. The survey forms were distributed and collected online by sharing the link to the survey form prepared via Google Forms. The research model was prepared in accordance with the purpose of the research explained above and is depicted in Figure 1.

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Figure 1. Research Model

In accordance with the research purpose and research model, this research has 20 hypotheses, including 3 main hypotheses and 17 sub-hypotheses:

H1: Applications implemented within the digital marketing mix affect online purchasing intention.

H1a: Applications regarding product carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.

H1b: Applications regarding price carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.

H1c: Applications regarding place carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.

H1d: Applications regarding promotion carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.

H1e: Applications regarding physical evidence carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.

H1f: Applications regarding process carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.

H1g: Applications regarding physical evidence carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.

H2: Online purchasing intention varies according to demographic variables.

H2a: Online purchasing intention differs by gender.

H2b: Online purchasing intention varies according to age.

H2c: Online purchasing intention varies according to marital status.

H2d: Online purchasing intention varies according to education level.

H2e: Online purchasing intention varies according to monthly income.

The data of the study were analyzed using SPSS 26.0 and AMOS 24 programs. For analyses; descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, arithmetic mean and standard deviation were used. Confirmatory factor analysis was performed to test the validity of the scales. To test the reliability of the scales, internal consistency coefficients (Cronbach's Alpha) were calculated. The normality of the data points was analyzed using skewness and kurtosis values. An independent sample t test and a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test were used to analyze differences between groups. The pearson product moment correlation test was used for relationship analyses. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for impact analysis. Statistical significance was sought within the 95% confidence interval.

4. Findings and Interpretation

The findings regarding the demographic information of the participants are presented in Table 1 below.

According to the findings in Table 1, approximately half of the participants were female (54.2%) and the other half were male (45.6%). The rate of participants aged between 18-25 is 19.8%, the rate of those between 26-30 is 31.7%, the rate of those between 31-35 is 21.0%, the rate of those between 36-40 is 14.1% and the rate of those who are 41 and over is 13.4%. Slightly more than half of the participants (54.5%) are single. While 35.4% of the participants were married, 10.1% of the participants were divorced. Approximately half of the participants (49.8%) have a bachelor's degree. The rate of those with a high school diploma or less is 16.1%, the rate of those with an associate degree is 11.1% and the rate of those with a postgraduate degree is 23.0%. When we look at the total monthly income of the participants, it is seen that the rate of those with an income of 9000 TL and below is 23.0%, the rate of those with an income of 9001-15000 TL is 37.4% and the rate of those with an income of 15001 TL and above is 39.6%.

Table 1. Demographic Information of Participants

Variables	Groups	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	185	45.8
	Female	219	54.2

Age	18-25	80	19.8
	26-30	128	31.7
	31-35	85	21.0
	36-40	57	14.1
	41 years and above	54	13.4
Marital status	Single	220	54.5
	Married	143	35.4
	Divorced	41	10.1
Educational Status	High school and below	65	16.1
	Associate Degree	45	11.1
	Graduate	201	49.8
	Postgraduate	93	23.0
Monthly Income	9000TL and below	93	23.0
	9001 – 15000TL	151	37.4
	15001TL and more	160	39.6

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed for the digital marketing mix elements used in the research model and the online purchasing intention scale. CFA was carried out using the AMOS 24 program in order to see to what extent the collected data fit the research model. As the first step of CFA, normality analysis was performed for the items on the scales. Skewness and kurtosis values were used

for normality analyses. Hair et al. (2010:78) and Byrne (2016:84) stated that in the social sciences, places can be considered normal if the skewness value is within ± 2 and the kurtosis value is within ± 7 . According to the findings in Table 2, since all skewness and kurtosis values were within the specified criterion values, the places were accepted to be normal and CFA was performed.

Table 2. Scale Items Normality Analysis Findings

Items	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
Intention2	1.00	5.00	-1.02	0.54
Intention1	1.00	5.00	-0.91	0.43
DMM40	1.00	5.00	-0.51	-0.24
DMM39	1.00	5.00	-0.54	-0.21
DMM38	1.00	5.00	-0.51	-0.35
DMM37	1.00	5.00	-0.62	-0.22
DMM36	1.00	5.00	-0.66	-0.16
DMM35	1.00	5.00	-0.58	-0.44
DMM34	1.00	5.00	-1.22	1.63
DMM33	1.00	5.00	-0.67	-0.23
DMM32	1.00	5.00	-1.49	2.58
DMM31	1.00	5.00	-1.30	2.45
DMM30	1.00	5.00	-1.28	2.70
DMM29	1.00	5.00	-0.80	0.66
DMM28	1.00	5.00	-0.74	0.18

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DMM27	1.00	5.00	-0.98	1.09
DMM26	1.00	5.00	-1.02	1.40
DMM25	1.00	5.00	-1.03	1.46
DMM24	1.00	5.00	-0.97	1.23
DMM23	1.00	5.00	-1.42	2.37
DMM22	1.00	5.00	-0.52	-0.58
DMM21	1.00	5.00	-0.69	-0.57
DMM20	1.00	5.00	-1.10	0.66
DMM19	1.00	5.00	-1.04	0.67
DMM18	1.00	5.00	-0.95	0.97
DMM17	1.00	5.00	-1.55	3.01
DMM16	1.00	5.00	-0.87	0.82
DMM15	1.00	5.00	-1.01	0.98
DMM14	1.00	5.00	-1.59	3.46
DMM13	1.00	5.00	-1.56	3.08
DMM12	1.00	5.00	-1.05	0.85
DMM11	1.00	5.00	-1.13	1.11
DMM10	1.00	5.00	-1.31	1.87
DMM9	1.00	5.00	-0.61	-0.40
DMM8	1.00	5.00	-1.30	2.14
DMM7	1.00	5.00	-0.38	-0.84
DMM6	1.00	5.00	-1.52	2.98
DMM5	1.00	5.00	-1.04	1.07
DMM4	1.00	5.00	-1.04	1.37
DMM3	1.00	5.00	-1.14	1.47
DMM2	1.00	5.00	-1.05	1.46
DMM1	1.00	5.00	-1.39	2.78

*DMM: Digital Marketing Mix

CFA was performed by including the scales of all variables in the research model into the analysis as a whole, and the analysis findings are shown in Table 3 and Table 4.

Table 3. Confirmatory Factor Analysis Findings of the Model

Items		Factor	β_0	β_1	SH	C.R.	p
DMM1	<----	Product	0.87	1.00			
DMM2	<----	Product	0.89	1.08	0.04	25,21	0.001
DMM3	<----	Product	0.91	1.10	0.04	26.88	0.001
DMM4	<----	Product	0.83	1.06	0.05	21.92	0.001
DMM5	<----	Product	0.79	1.07	0.05	20,19	0.001
DMM6	<----	Product	0.73	0.82	0.05	17.97	0.001
DMM7	<----	Price	0.51	1.00			

DMM8	<----	Price	0.80	1.04	0.10	10.53	0.001
DMM9	<----	Price	0.55	1.00	0.12	8.58	0.001
DMM10	<----	Price	0.83	1.11	0.10	10.71	0.001
DMM11	<----	Price	0.83	1.18	0.11	10.71	0.001
DMM12	<----	Place	0.70	1.00			
DMM13	<----	Place	0.86	1.00	0.06	16.48	0.001
DMM14	<----	Place	0.88	0.95	0.06	16.87	0.001
DMM15	<----	Place	0.74	1.00	0.07	14.26	0.001
DMM16	<----	Place	0.68	0.89	0.07	13,17	0.001
DMM17	<----	Place	0.79	0.97	0.06	15,16	0.001
DMM18	<----	Promotion	0.80	1.00			
DMM19	<----	Promotion	0.84	1.14	0.06	19.41	0.001
DMM20	<----	Promotion	0.90	1.22	0.06	21.48	0.001
DMM21	<----	Promotion	0.78	1.31	0.08	17.49	0.001
DMM22	<----	Promotion	0.58	0.94	0.08	12.29	0.001
DMM23	<----	Promotion	0.81	1.00	0.05	18.69	0.001
DMM24	<----	Physical Evi- dence	0.89	1.00			
DMM25	<----	Physical Evi- dence	0.88	0.98	0.04	25.83	0.001
DMM26	<----	Physical Evi- dence	0.92	1.01	0.04	28.62	0.001
DMM27	<----	Physical Evi- dence	0.90	0.97	0.04	27.41	0.001
DMM28	<----	Physical Evi- dence	0.70	0.93	0.05	17.20	0.001
DMM29	<----	Physical Evi- dence	0.79	0.93	0.05	20.78	0.001
DMM30	<----	Process	0.92	1.00			
DMM31	<----	Process	0.93	1.10	0.03	32.66	0.001
DMM32	<----	Process	0.86	1.07	0.04	26.31	0.001
DMM33	<----	Process	0.54	0.88	0.07	12,19	0.001
DMM34	<----	Process	0.82	1.09	0.05	23.72	0.001
DMM35	<----	People	0.84	1.00			
DMM36	<----	People	0.86	0.95	0.04	22.86	0.001
DMM37	<----	People	0.77	0.87	0.05	18.89	0.001
DMM38	<----	People	0.95	1.05	0.04	27.67	0.001
DMM39	<----	People	0.96	1.04	0.04	28.43	0.001
DMM40	<----	People	0.97	1.04	0.04	28.46	0.001
Intention1	<----	Online Purc- hase Intention	0.73	1.00			
Intention2	<----	Online Purc- hase Intention	0.56	1.05	0.04	28.86	0.001

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According to the findings in Table 3, it is seen that all regression weights are significant in the first model in which all factors and items are included and tested. When the standardized parameter estimate values were examined, it was determined that all values were higher than 0.50 and the lowest standardized parameter estimate value was 0.51.

Table 4. CFA Model Fit Index Findings

Fit Index	Perfect Fit	Acceptable Fit	Original Model	Modified Model
CMIN	< 2.00	< 3.00	4.53	3.57
RMR	< 0.05	< 0.10	0.09	0.09
NFI	> 0.95	> 0.90	0.80	0.85
CFI	> 0.95	> 0.90	0.84	0.88
GFI	> 0.95	> 0.90	0.63	0.71
AGFI	> 0.90	> 0.85	0.58	0.66
RMSEA	< 0.05	< 0.10	0.09	0.08

Model fit indices of the CFA model are also shown in Table 4. When the model fit indices were examined, it was determined that the RMR and RMSEA values were below the 0.10 criterion value. On the other hand, it was determined that the CMIN, CFI, GFI, AGFI and NFI values did not meet the criterion values. To increase model fit, modification index values were examined and suggested covariance connections were made within the same factor. When the model fit indices for the modified model were examined, it was seen that the RMR and RMSEA values met the criteria. It was observed that the CMIN value of 3.57 was very close to the criterion value of 3.00. Similarly, it was observed that the GFI values of 0.88 and the NFI of 0.85 were very close to the criterion value of 0.90. Therefore, it was accepted that the RMR, RMSEA, CMIN, CFI and NFI criteria were met. It is seen that there are increases in GFI and AGFI values after the modification and they become much closer to the criterion values. Since values were met for five of the seven criteria used, the CFA model was considered to have an acceptable fit (Hurley et al., 1997).

Table 5. Reliability Analysis of the Scales Used in the Research

Scales	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Product	6	0.93
Price	5	0.83
Place	6	0.90
Promotion	6	0.90

Physical Evidence	6	0.93
Process	5	0.89
People	6	0.96
Online Purchase Intention	2	0.93

Internal consistency coefficients (Cronbach's Alpha) were calculated to test the reliability of the scales used in the research (Table 5). Scales with internal consistency coefficients of 0.80 and above are considered to be highly reliable scales (Nakip and Yaraş, 2017:196). The internal consistency coefficients of all the scales used in this research were measured at 0.80 and above, and therefore these scales were accepted as high reliability scales.

The structural model shown in the research model was tested and the test results are shown in Table 6 below.

Table 6. Test Results of the Structural Model of the Research

Dependent Variables	Factor	β	SH	R2	p
Online Purchase Intention	Product	-0.01	0.08	0.58	0.89
Online Purchase Intention	Place	-0.06	0.07		0.27
Online Purchase Intention	Price	0.09	0.08		0.18
Online Purchase Intention	Promotion	-0.01	0.06		0.84
Online Purchase Intention	Physical Evidence	-0.23	0.09		0.00
Online Purchase Intention	Process	0.30	0.08		0.00
Online Purchase Intention	People	0.01	0.04		0.80

According to the findings in the table above; it has been determined that the effect of applications related to physical evidence ($\beta=-0.23, p<0.05$) and process ($\beta=0.30, p<0.05$) on online purchasing intention were significant, but the effect of applications related to product, price, place, promotion and people on online purchasing intention are not significant. While the effect of physical evidence on online purchasing intention is negative, the effect of process on online purchasing intention is positive. According to these findings, when applications related to the physical evidence increase, online purchasing intention decreases, while when applications related to the process increase, the level of online purchasing

intention also increases.

The findings of the analysis regarding whether there are differences according to the demographic characteristics of the participants in terms of online purchasing intention levels are presented in this section. In this context, it was analyzed whether online purchasing intention levels differ according to the gender, age, marital status, education level and monthly income of the participants. Table 7 shows the findings of the difference analysis of online purchase intention levels by gender, age, marital status, education level and monthly income of the participants.

Table 7. Online Purchasing Intention and Gender T-Test Results

	Gender	n	Cover.	Ss.	Levene Test		ttest	
					F	P	t	p
Online Purchase Intention	Male	185	4.05	0.88	0.45	0.50	-1.81	0.07
	Female	219	4.20	0.86				

According to the findings in Table 7; it has been observed that participants levels of intention to shop via e-commerce site do not differ statistically significantly according to the gender of the participants

($t=-1.81$ and $p>0.05$). In other words, the intention levels of male and female participants to shop on the e-commerce site are similar.

Table 8. Online Purchasing Intention and Age, Marital Status, Education Level and Monthly Income F-Test Results

	Age	n	\bar{X}	Ss		KT	sd.	KO	F	p	
Online Purchasing Intention	18-25	80	3.81	1.03	Between-group	20.87	4	5.22	7.29	0.00	b>a
	26-30	128	4.33	0.76	Within-group	285.67	399	0.72			
	31-35	85	4.29	0.75	Total	306.55	403				
	36-40	57	4.20	0.81							
	41 +	54	3.81	0.90							
	Marital status	n	\bar{X}	Ss		KT	sd.	KO	F	p	
Online Purchasing Intention	Single	220	4.08	0.90	Between-group	3.96	2	1.98	2.62	0.07	
	Married	143	4.26	0.76	Within-group	302.59	401	0.75			
	Divorced	41	3.98	1.05	Total	306.55	403				

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	Education level	n	\bar{X}	Ss		KT	sd.	KO	F	p	
Online Purchasing Intention	High school and below	65	3.58	1.09	Between-group	26.19	3	8.73	12.45	0.00	a<b
	Associate degree	45	4.10	0.70	Within-group	280.36	400	0.70			a<c
	Graduate	201	4.21	0.84	Total	306.55	403				a<d
	Postgraduate	93	4.36	0.67							
	Monthly Income	n	\bar{X}	Ss		KT	sd.	KO	F	p	
Online Purchasing Intention	9000 TL and -	93	3.95	0.98	Between-group	9.53	2	4.76	6.43	0.00	a<c
	9001-15000 TL	151	4.05	0.90	Within-group	297.02	401	0.74			b<c
	15001 TL and +	160	4.32	0.74	Total	306.55	403				

According to the findings in Table 8; it was observed that participants' levels of intention to shop on e-commerce sites differ statistically significantly depending on the age of the participants ($F=7.29$ and $p<0.05$). Post Hoc analyzes were performed using the Bonferroni technique to see which age groups there was a significant difference. It was determined that the significant difference was between the 26-30 and 31-35 age groups and the 18-25 and 41+ age groups in favor of the 26-30 and 31-35 age groups. Participants' levels of intention to shop on e-commerce sites do not differ statistically significantly according to the marital status of the participants (for F value; $p>0.05$). In other words, even if the marital status of the participants differs, their level of intention to shop on the e-commerce site does not differ. Participants levels of intention to shop on e-commerce sites differ statistically significantly according

to their education level of the participants ($F=12.45$ and $p<0.05$). Post Hoc analyzes were performed using the Bonferroni technique to see which age groups there was a significant difference. It was determined that the significant difference was between the high school and below group and other education groups. Participants levels of intention to shop on e-commerce sites differ statistically significantly according to their monthly income of the participants ($F=6.43$ and $p<0.05$). Post Hoc analyzes were performed using the Bonferroni technique to see which age groups there was a significant difference. It was determined that the significant difference was between the 15001 TL and above group and other monthly income groups.

As a result of the analysis, the summary table of hypothesis test results is as follows.

Table 9. Hypothesis Test Results

No.	Hypotheses	Conclusion
H1	Applications implemented within the digital marketing mix affect online purchasing intention.	Partially Accepted
H1a	Applications regarding product carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.	Rejected
H1b	Applications regarding price carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.	Rejected
H1c	Applications regarding place carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.	Rejected

H1d	Applications regarding promotion carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.	Rejected
H1e	Applications regarding physical evidence carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.	Accepted
H1f	Applications regarding process carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.	Accepted
H1g	Applications regarding physical evidence carried out in digital marketing affect online purchasing intention.	Rejected
H2	Online purchasing intention according to demographic variables becomes different.	Partially Accepted
H2a	Online purchasing intention differs according to gender.	Rejected
H2b	Online purchasing intention varies according to age.	Accepted
H2c	Online purchasing intention varies according to marital status.	Rejected
H2d	Online purchasing intention varies according to education level.	Accepted
H2e	Online purchasing intention varies according to monthly income.	Accepted

Main hypothesis H1 (Digital marketing mix activities affect online purchasing intention); Sub hypotheses H1e, and H1f were accepted, but they were partially accepted because sub hypotheses H1a, H1b, H1c, H1d, and H1g were rejected. Main hypothesis H2 (Online purchasing intention differs according to demographic variables); Sub hypotheses H2b, H2d and H2e were accepted, but they were partially accepted because sub hypotheses H2a and H2c were rejected.

5. Result

In our age, the diversity and similarity of the products offered on the internet have increased competition to very high levels. Companies have had to use all their resources to make their products accepted by consumers online. This point in technology has offered opportunities and innovations for consumers and started a very difficult process for businesses. Businesses that have been able to reach consumers easily with the internet have now started to have problems ensuring that their products hold on to the digital market. In order to gain a competitive advantage, e-businesses aim to develop their products, offer them more advantageously than their competitors, and ensure that their products are perceived as superior to their competitors by the consumer. In this context, e-commerce companies have begun to investigate what appropriate the marketing mix strategies could be to integrate with the audiences they address. The marketing mix is the set of variables

that can affect consumers' purchasing decisions and can be controlled to a large extent by businesses. Marketing mix decisions are decisions about how to distribute financial and organizational resources, capacities and skills among marketing mix elements. With marketing mix decisions, managers try to meet the demands and expectations of their customers while also trying to achieve the goals and objectives of their businesses. In order to establish a mutual and continuous relationship between the business and the target market by bringing the marketing mix elements together appropriately and to ensure a satisfactory change, the elements that make up the marketing mix must be very well. Therefore, decisions regarding this issue must be carefully designed, implemented effectively, and the results constantly evaluated.

Due to the importance mentioned above, this research aims to investigate the effect of product, price, place, promotion, physical evidence, process and people on online purchasing intention. Additionally, it was also aimed at measure whether online purchase intentions differ according to participants' demographic characteristics. This research has an important role in filling the gap in the literature. It will contribute to a better understanding of the e-commerce phenomenon and increase customer satisfaction by determining the factors affecting online purchasing intention.

The data was obtained through a survey conducted via Google Forms in January 2023. The population

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of the research consists of 404 adults over the age of 18 who live in Turkey and have shopped online at least once in a certain period of their lives. The data from the study were analyzed using SPSS 26.0 and AMOS 24.0 programs. According to the findings of the research; it can be stated that marketing mix elements partially affect online purchasing intention. According to this; it has been concluded that physical evidence and process elements positively and directly affect online purchasing intention. Difference analyses of the research according to demographic characteristics show that some elements of the online purchasing intention differ. According to this, it can be stated that online purchasing intention varies according to age, education level and monthly income. When past studies on the subject are analyzed, it is observed that the digital marketing mix is mostly analyzed through the 4Ps (Abrar et al., 2016; Baltes, 2016; Sriram et al., 2019; Ratnadianti et al., 2020; Kebede et al., 2023). In this study, unlike other studies, analysis was carried out through 7Ps. On the other hand, it has been observed that studies evaluating the digital marketing mix through 7 Ps mostly focus on SMEs (Gutiérrez and Trujillo, 2016), marketing performance (Yusuf et al., 2022), the tourism sector (Matura, 2018), locational advantage (Fachriyan, 2022), the fashion sector (Wahyuni et al., 2023) and chain market performance (Al-Sukar and Alabboodi, 2020). In this study, the relationship between 7Ps and online purchase intention was observed.

Based on these results obtained from the research, some suggestions can be made for practitioners and future researchers. Since this research found that digital marketing elements positively affect online purchasing intention, practitioners should act in maximum compliance with digital marketing mix elements in e-commerce applications in order to increase e-commerce volume. In particular, much more attention should be paid to the physical evidence and process, that have significant positive effects. It can be also expressed that practitioners should consider customers' demographic characteristics to increase online purchasing intention.

Based on the results of this research, some suggestions can be made for future researchers. Future studies should repeat similar studies using different and larger sample groups. Future studies should add different independent variables to the research model used in this study and examine the relationships of these variables with the marketing mix and purchasing intention in the digital environment.

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